

SIMULATION OF INTERMEDIATE DEBONDING IN FRP-STRENGTHENED RC BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Flexural FRP-strengthening of reinforced concrete (RC) beams often leads to brittle failure modes induced by a debonding originated at the plate end (either plate end debonding or concrete cover rip-off) or induced by an intermediate crack (IC). In this last case, debonding initiates at a major flexural crack and then propagates towards a plate end. However, in spite of it being the dominant failure mode in certain circumstances, such as thin FRP plates, the number of studies regarding the IC debonding mechanism is limited.

It is the purpose of this work to present a one-dimensional simplified numerical model based on spectral elements and on the discrete crack approach that for practical applications can truly represent the structural response of flexural FRP-strengthened concrete beams. The discrete crack approach is employed to consider geometrical discontinuities such as flexural cracks and debonding of the FRP sheet, originated from the tip the flexural crack. This model is able to provide a sound mechanical description and interpretation of the phenomena leading to failure of FRP-retrofitted RC beams in a very simple way and with low computational cost.

The proposed new element is formulated in such a way that when a geometrical discontinuity appears, one only needs to replace the original spectral element with the new spectral element with embedded crack, keeping the original nodes unaltered. Hence, the insertion of this element in a modular approach is suitable for faster modelling since the perturbation on the original mesh is minor. Furthermore, to avoid the assumption of a previous crack pattern, the size of the elements is chosen considering different evaluation formulas of the mean crack spacing.

The applicability of the proposed method is discussed by comparing the analysis results with the experimental results obtained from static four-point loading tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) plates or sheets are increasingly used for the strengthening of reinforced concrete (RC) structures due to their numerous advantages [1, 2]. However, one of the main disadvantages with this technique is the plate debonding induced by an intermediate crack (IC). There are few studies regarding the IC debonding mechanism. Most studies are based on refined 2D and 3D finite element (FE) simulations using the smeared-crack approach [3-6] although the discrete crack approach has also been used in some FE analyses [7, 8]. Less expensive one-dimensional models have been also applied [9, 10].

It is the purpose of this work to implement a one-dimensional discrete crack approach that can truly represent the structural response of flexural FRP-strengthened concrete beams. The discrete crack model is employed to consider geometrical discontinuities such as flexural cracks and debonding of the FRP sheet, originated from the tip the flexural crack. The model is based on the Timoshenko theory and is solved by using spectral elements [11, 12]. Spectral methods [11, 12] allow solving problems to high accuracy in a simple domain, such as that corresponding to the strengthened beam, allowing significant reductions in the computational load. Furthermore, they are especially suitable to represent the dynamic behaviour of FRP-strengthened RC structures placing a special focus on the influence of the interfacial intermediate debonding mechanism on the mentioned behaviour [13].

2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In the present section the governing differential equations for the proposed problem are derived. On the basis of such equations the spectral finite element method will be applied.

To solve the kinematics of the problem, firstly the partial interaction between RC beam and FRP plate is reflected by using an interface-slip s , which can be expressed as

$$s = u_{FRP,top} - u_{C,bot} \quad (1)$$

with $u_{FRP,top}$ and $u_{C,bot}$ denoting the axial displacements at the top of the FRP plate and at the bottom of the RC beam, respectively (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Kinematic of the transverse section of FRP-strengthened RC beam

According to the first-order shear deformation theory, the displacement field for axial and transverse motion is obtained by expanding the displacements in a Taylor series about the mid-plane displacements, $u_0(x,t)$ and $w(x,t)$, as

$$u_C(x, z, t) = u_0(x, t) - z\phi(x, t) \quad (2)$$

$$u_{FRP}(x, z, t) = u_0(x, t) - z\phi(x, t) + s(x, t) \quad (3)$$

$$w(x, z, t) = w(x, t) \quad (4)$$

where u_C , u_{FRP} and w are respectively the axial displacements in RC beam and FRP plate and the transverse displacement at a material point. ϕ is the curvature-independent rotation of the beam cross-section about the Y-axis. The coordinate z is measured from the mid-plane. These kinematic relationships are kept for the beam sections in which there is no FRP by removing the terms concerning the external reinforcement.

Using equations (2), (3) and (4), the linear strains can be written as

$$\varepsilon_{x,C} = u_{0,x} - z\phi_{,x} \quad \gamma_{xz,C} = w_{,x} - \phi \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_{x,FRP} = u_{0,x} - z\phi_{,x} + s_{,x} \quad \gamma_{xz,FRP} = w_{,x} - \phi \quad (6)$$

Here $(\cdot)_{,x}$ represents differentiation with respect to x .

Furthermore, the shear strain in the adhesive $\gamma_{xz,AD}$ can be calculated from the interface-slip s and its thickness

$$\gamma_{xz,AD} = s/e_{AD} \quad (7)$$

where e_{AD} denotes the thickness of the adhesive.

The linear constitutive model for the concrete beam and the FRP plate can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{x,C} = E_C \varepsilon_{x,C} \quad \tau_{xz,C} = G_C \gamma_{xz,C} \quad (8)$$

$$\tau_{xz,FRP} = G_{FRP} \gamma_{xz,FRP} \quad (9)$$

where the material constants, E and G , are referred to the concrete beam (C) or the external plate (FRP) depending on the material considered.

Calculation of bond shear stress between the FRP and concrete is very important in order to check the debonding failure mode. Its value along a certain length of beam can be expressed as a function of the axial force acting on the FRP plate. Based upon the hypothesis on linear behaviour of the adhesive interface, the following relationship can be assumed

$$\tau_{xz,AD} = F_{FRP,x} = k_{AD} s = G_{AD} \gamma_{xz,AD} \quad (10)$$

where F_{FRP} is the axial force in the plate, $k_{AD} = G_{AD} / e_{AD}$ is the shear stiffness of the adhesive and G_{AD} is the elastic shear modulus of the adhesive.

By application of Hamilton's principle the governing equations of the FRP flexural strengthened RC beam are obtained and can be written as

$$\delta u_0 : I_0 \ddot{u}_0 - I_1 \ddot{\phi} + I_{0,FRP} \ddot{s} - A_{11} u_{0,xx} + B_{11} \phi_{,xx} - A_{FRP} s_{,xx} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\delta w : I_0 \ddot{w} - A_{22} w_{,xx} + A_{22} \phi_{,x} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\delta \phi : I_2 \ddot{\phi} - I_1 \ddot{u}_0 - I_{1,FRP} \ddot{s} + B_{11} u_{0,xx} - D_{11} \phi_{,xx} - A_{22} w_{,x} + A_{22} \phi + B_{FRP} s_{,xx} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\delta s : I_{0,FRP} \ddot{s} + I_{0,FRP} \ddot{u}_0 - I_{1,FRP} \ddot{\phi} - A_{FRP} s_{,xx} - A_{FRP} u_{0,xx} + B_{FRP} \phi_{,xx} + \frac{G_{AD} s b_{AD}}{e_{AD}} = 0 \quad (14)$$

and the associated force boundary equations can be expressed as

$$N = A_{11} u_{0,x} - B_{11} \phi_{,x} + A_{FRP} s_{,x} \quad (15)$$

$$V = A_{22} w_{,x} - A_{22} \phi \quad (16)$$

$$M = -B_{11} u_{0,x} + D_{11} \phi_{,x} - B_{FRP} s_{,x} \quad (17)$$

$$N^* = A_{FRP} s_{,x} + A_{FRP} u_{0,x} - B_{FRP} \phi_{,x} \quad (18)$$

where (\cdot) denotes temporal derivative. N , V , M and N^* are the stress resultants associated with the variables u_0 , w , ϕ and s , respectively. A_{11} , B_{11} , D_{11} , A_{22} , A_{FRP} and B_{FRP} are the stiffness coefficients and I_0 , I_1 and I_2 are the inertial coefficients.

3 FORMULATION OF THE SPECTRAL ELEMENT

The fast Fourier transformation (FFT)-based spectral element method (SEM) was proposed by Doyle [14] and is very similar to the finite element method as far as the assembly and the solution of the equation of motion is concerned. Using the spectral element method, the general solution of the governing equations of motion, $\{u\} = (u_0(x,t), w(x,t), \phi(x,t), s(x,t))$, is represented by a spectral form as follows

$$\{u\} = \sum_{n=1}^N \{ \hat{u}(x, \omega_n) \} e^{-j\omega_n t} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \{ \hat{u}_{mn}^* \} e^{-jk_{mn} x} \right) e^{-j\omega_n t} \quad (19)$$

where ω_n is the circular frequency at the n th sampling point and N is the frequency index corresponding to the Nyquist frequency in Fast Fourier Transform (FFT); k_{mn} is the m th wave number for the frequency ω_n . $\{ \hat{u} \}$ represents the spectral amplitude vector corresponding to the generic

displacement vector as a function of (x, ω_n) and $\{\hat{u}_{mn}^*\} = (\hat{u}_0, \hat{w}, \hat{\phi}, \hat{s})_{mn}$ represents the wave coefficient vector associated with the m th mode of wave and for each frequency, ω_n .

Substituting (14) into (6)-(9) the characteristic equation is obtained whose resolution will give the eight roots or wavenumbers k_{mn} for each value of the frequency ω_n which correspond to the different modes of the solution. Each wavenumber k_{mn} acts as a scale factor on the displacement variable in the same way that the frequency acts on the time.

Once the wavenumbers have been computed for each particular frequency ω_n the complex dynamic stiffness matrix is formed from the amplitude ratio matrix by using the force boundary conditions. The assembled system of spectral elements is solved at each sampling frequency. The time history of the field variables can then be post-processed using inverse FFT. More details about the derivation of the dynamic stiffness matrix can be found in [13].

The static formulation of the method is straightforward from the dynamic formulation by making the frequency tend to zero.

4 DISCRETE CRACK ELEMENT

A simplified discrete crack approach has been proposed to simulate the initialization and propagation of intermediate debonding for FRP sheet due to flexural cracks. For it, a new spectral element with embedded crack is developed to replace the original element when a geometrical discontinuity appears. The nodes of the original element, which are used for the assembly with the rest of the element mesh, remain unaltered in the new element; in this way, the introduction of the new element causes few disturbances in the procedure.

In the presence of an intermediate crack (Fig.2a), the original element is reformulated to consider this effect. With the appearance of crack the length of the element L_e is divided into three segments of lengths L_1 , L_2 and L_3 in such a way that $L_e=L_1+L_2+L_3$ and the number of subelements increases from one to six (Fig. 2b). Crack is assumed to be at a distance of $L_1+L_2/2$ from the node 1 and its height is h_1 . Subelements 1 and 2 are treated as base-strengthened beams without crack and debonding while the intermediate section has been divided into four subelements to represent the crack effects: the through-height discontinuity between third and fourth subelements represents the flexural crack; meanwhile the materials above and below the crack (subelements 5 and 6) of heights h_2 and e_F , respectively, represent concrete and FRP, respectively. Nodes of the subelements 3 and 4 are located at the mid-height of the flexural crack.

Figure 2. (a) Two-node original element before the appearance of the flexural crack and location of the flexural crack; (b) Reconfiguration of the element after the flexural crack

In the same way, a length of debonding equal to L_2 has been assumed associated with the crack since the materials above and below debonding, i.e. concrete (subelements 3 and 4) and FRP (subelement 6), are treated as two beams separated out from the strengthened beam. This length might be assumed initially equal to the crack width and, subsequently, according to the evolution of the slip at the FRP-concrete interface might be expanded with the progressive debonding at the concrete-FRP interface.

The power of the proposed discrete crack model is due to its simplicity and possibility to be extended also in the case of other types of failure mode.

The kinematic relationships relating the nodal degrees of freedom at the left vertical interfaces are as follows

$$\{\hat{u}_7\} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_7^0 \\ \hat{w}_7 \\ \hat{\phi}_7 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_5^0 + \frac{h+e_F}{2}\hat{\phi}_5 + \hat{s}_5 \\ \hat{w}_5 \\ \hat{\phi}_5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \frac{h+e_F}{2} & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_5^0 \\ \hat{w}_5 \\ \hat{\phi}_5 \\ \hat{s}_5 \end{pmatrix} = [S_1]\{\hat{u}_5\} \quad (20)$$

$$\{\hat{u}_8\} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_8^0 \\ \hat{w}_8 \\ \hat{\phi}_8 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_5^0 + \frac{h-h_1}{2}\hat{\phi}_5 \\ \hat{w}_5 \\ \hat{\phi}_5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \frac{h-h_1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_5^0 \\ \hat{w}_5 \\ \hat{\phi}_5 \\ \hat{s}_5 \end{pmatrix} = [S_2]\{\hat{u}_5\} \quad (21)$$

$$\{\hat{u}_9\} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_9^0 \\ \hat{w}_9 \\ \hat{\phi}_9 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_5^0 - \frac{h-h_2}{2}\hat{\phi}_5 \\ \hat{w}_5 \\ \hat{\phi}_5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & -\frac{h-h_2}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u}_5^0 \\ \hat{w}_5 \\ \hat{\phi}_5 \\ \hat{s}_5 \end{pmatrix} = [S_3]\{\hat{u}_5\} \quad (22)$$

Similarly for the right vertical interfaces we have

$$\{\hat{u}_{10}\} = [S_1]\{\hat{u}_6\} \quad (23)$$

$$\{\hat{u}_{11}\} = [S_2]\{\hat{u}_6\} \quad (24)$$

$$\{\hat{u}_{12}\} = [S_3]\{\hat{u}_6\} \quad (25)$$

According to Eq. (14), the overhead hat indicates that the variables are discretized in the frequency domain.

From Fig. 3 the force balance at the interface between the base beam subelement 1 and the subelements 3, 5 and 6 is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \hat{N}_5 \\ \hat{V}_5 \\ \hat{M}_5 \\ \hat{N}_5^* \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \hat{N}_7 \\ \hat{V}_7 \\ \hat{M}_7 + \frac{h+e_F}{2}\hat{N}_7 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \hat{N}_8 \\ \hat{V}_8 \\ \hat{M}_8 + \frac{h-h_1}{2}\hat{N}_8 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \hat{N}_9 \\ \hat{V}_9 \\ \hat{M}_9 - \frac{h-h_2}{2}\hat{N}_9 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \hat{N}_{5FRP}^* \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (26)$$

where N, V, M and N* are the stress resultants associated with the variables u_0 , w , ϕ and s , respectively.

A similar relation would be obtained at the interface between subelement 2 and subelements 4, 5 and 6.

Figure 3. Force balance

At the crack surface, under the assumption of no contact between the surfaces adjacent to the crack, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \hat{f}_3 \} &= 0 \\ \{ \hat{f}_4 \} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

5 COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The proposed discrete approach has been implemented by using an iterative secant approach based on replacing the initial tangent elastic moduli for the concrete, the steel reinforcement and the adhesive by equivalent secant elastic moduli when nonlinear behaviour of material begins.

To evaluate the accuracy of the proposed numerical model for IC debonding, the results of a FRP-plated beam experimentally tested in [15] were used. The failure mode of the specimen used for comparison was initiated by midspan debonding. Using the proposed approach, the load-deflection behaviour as well as the distribution of interface stresses of strengthened beams may be obtained.

One FRP-strengthened RC beams (BF2) and its corresponding unstrengthened RC beam (BF1) were used to validate proposed approach. Geometrical data of the chosen specimen as well as loading configuration is shown in Fig.4. The material properties are: (a) Concrete: Elastic modulus=28580 MPa, compressive strength= 36.5 MPa; (b) FRP: Elastic modulus= 159 GPa, tensile strength= 3200 MPa; (c) Steel: Yield strength= 590 MPa, elastic modulus= 200 MPa.

Figure 4. FRP-strengthened RC beam

To define the mesh, only one element was used for the portion of the non-strengthened beam close to the support considering its uniformity and that cracking phenomenon will not occur in that area and an element size of 100 mm was adopted for the strengthened beam. Only half of the specimen was modelled by taking advantage of symmetry. The size of the elements might even be increased in those areas of the strengthened portion close to the FRP plate ends in which cracking will not occur. Compared with the conventional FE models, in the proposed approach the number of elements has been reduced drastically.

Fig. 5 illustrates the comparison of the spectral model prediction of the load-deflection response for the FRP-strengthened beam along with the experimental results. The results show that the predicted ultimate load of the specimen agrees well with the experimental data. Predictions obtained in [6] with a refined FE model of 11014 finite elements are also shown. However, the accuracy of the proposed simplified model can be considered very good considering that a mesh of only 20 elements was used. Numerical predictions and experimental results for reference unstrengthened beam are also shown in Fig. 5. For these unstrengthened specimens the agreement between experimental and numerical results is also good.

Figure 5. Load-displacement comparison

The local behaviour at the adhesive-concrete interface considering flexural cracking of the RC beam is shown in Fig. 6 by using the FRP strain profile. The strain in the FRP is a maximum at the crack positions as the tensile strain is resisted solely by the FRP. The strain in the FRP between the cracks decreases as both the FRP and concrete resist the tensile strains. Comparisons were made with the experimental results [15] and with the numerical predictions under ultimate load carried out in [6]. The experimental test maximum strain values for both specimens are also shown. As expected, there is a strong increase in the strain at failure at the loading points characteristic of the interfacial debonding at the more loaded region. In general, the predicted values of the maximum longitudinal strain in the FRP plate at debonding failure between the two concentrated loads are in good agreement with the experimental strain values used for comparison, considering the simplicity of the model used. Some disagreement appears for the most external regions due to that the model is not able to simulate shear cracks.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A new discrete crack approach in a one-dimensional framework has been presented in this paper for the numerical prediction of IC debonding failures in FRP-strengthened RC beams. The model correlates well with test data globally and locally and can be used to predict IC debonding with

confidence where debonding is governed by the bond–slip behaviour of the FRP-to-concrete interface. Furthermore, the model is especially efficient in both cost and complexity.

Figure 6. FRP strain profile

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